

**VI Simpozijum Srpskog udruženja za
proteomiku (SePA)
“Razvoj i primena novih metoda
proteomike”**

**Rektorat Univerziteta u Kragujevcu
2. jun 2023. godine**

Book of abstracts

**VI Simpozijum Srpskog udruženja za proteomiku:
“Razvoj i primena novih metoda proteomike”**

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VI Simpozijum Srpskog udruženja za proteomiku “Razvoj i primena novih metoda proteomike”

13:00 **Prof. dr Marija Stanić** - dekan PMF Kragujevac, **Prof. dr Nevena Đukić**, PMF- Kragujevac, otvaranje VI SePA simpozijuma.

13:10 **Dr Lidija Izrael – Živković**, “Proteome changes of the model bacteria *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* san ai exposed to nanoceria”, Institut za hemiju, Medicinski fakultet, Univerzitet u Beogradu, Višegradska 26, Beograd, Srbija

13:30 **Dr Ana Medić**, “Flexibility of carbon catabolic pathways in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* san ai during the biodegradation of toxic organic compounds- a multiomics approach”, Institut za hemiju, Medicinski fakultet, Univerzitet u Beogradu, Višegradska 26, Beograd, Srbija

13:50 **Dr Katarina Smiljanić**, “Alterations in proteomic profiles of lung epithelial cell line BEAS 2B upon treatments with electronic cigarettes liquids and pure nicotine”, Univerzitet u Beogradu – Hemijski fakultet, Studentski trg 12-16, Beograd, Srbija

14:10 **Dr Nataša Avramović**, “Application of NMR spectroscopy in metabolomics”, Institut za hemiju, Medicinski fakultet, Univerzitet u Beogradu, Višegradska 26, Beograd, Srbija

14:30 **Dr Romana Masnikosa**, “Plasma profile of inflammatory mediators in NHL patients”, Institut za nuklearne nauke „Vinča“, Laboratorija za fizičku hemiju, Mike Petrovića Alasa 12-14 11351 Vinča, Beograd, Srbija

14:50 Pauza: Poster sekcija

15:10 **Dr Marko Živanović**, “Scaffolds for *in vivo* wound healing”, Institut za informacione tehnologije Kragujevac, Jovana Cvijića bb, 34000 Kragujevac.

15:30 **Dr Milan Mladenović**, “Computational Approaches in Modulating the Estrogen Receptor α ; Signaling: A Pathway for Breast Cancer Cure Discovery?”, Univerzitet u Kragujevcu, Prirodno – Matematički fakultet, Institut za Hemiju, Radoja Domanovića 12, Kragujevac, Srbija

15:50 **Dr Milena Milutinović**, „The impact of natural products on the expression of apoptosis and biotransformation-related genes and proteins in immortalized carcinoma cell lines” Univerzitet u Kragujevcu, Prirodno – Matematički fakultet, Institut za Biologiju i Ekologiju, Radoja Domanovića 12, Kragujevac, Srbija

16:10 **Dr Maja Krstić Ristivojević**,”Identification of isoforms of shellfish tropomyosin” Univerzitet u Beogradu – Hemijski fakultet, Studentski trg 12-16, Beograd, Srbija

16:30 **Dr Nikola Gligorijević**, “Biocorona formation of hen proteins onto the surface of polystyrene and polyethylene terephthalate”, Univerzitet u Beogradu – Hemijski fakultet, Studentski trg 12-16, Beograd, Srbija

16:50 **Dr Dragana Filipović**, “Chronic fluoxetine treatment of socially isolated rats modulates prefrontal cortex proteome”, Institut za nuklearne nauke „Vinča“, Laboratorija za molekularnu biologiju i endokrinologiju, Mike Petrovića Alasa 12-14 11351 Vinča, Beograd, Srbija

17:10 Analysis doo

17:30 Diskusija i zatvaranje skupa

18:00 Godišnja skupština društva

Identification of isoforms of shellfish tropomyosin

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From over 10 kg in 1960 to over 20 kg in 2014, the yearly per capita consumption of marine products has increased significantly during the past 50 years. In many nations, especially those with poor overall protein intake, seafood protein is a crucial component of the diet¹. However, as defined by the European Community shellfish protein tropomyosin (TPM) is one of the major allergens and major causes of anaphylaxis². Although TPM originating from vertebrates is not considered as an allergen there is evidence that several fish tropomyosin can be allergenic³. TPM protein is organized of two parallel alpha-helical molecules which are wound around each other forming a coiled-coil structure². Although the degree of similarity between TPM molecules is high, their allergenic potency is different. Scientists putting a lot of effort into identifying and sequencing tropomyosin isoforms since this information probably explains the intriguing nature of the TPM molecule. This is a very challenging task given that the differences in mass and pI values between TPM isoforms are discrete.

TPM was isolated from mussels (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*), and clams (*Venerupis philippinarum*) according to the protocol developed within/and for purposes of the IMPTOX research project. The obtained “in-house” TPM proteins were resolved using two-dimensional polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (2D-PAGE). Isoelectric focusing was performed on rehydrated Immobiline strips IPG3-5.6NL 13 cm in Ettan IPGPhor 3 device. The second dimension was carried out on 12% PAA gels. Upon protein bands excision to prevent TPM interchain disulfide cross-linking reduction and alkylation of cysteine was performed. The samples were digested with proteomics-grade trypsin in a 1:50 enzyme-to-substrate ratio overnight at 37 °C. The obtained peptides were chromatographically separated using the EASY-nLC II system and analyzed using Orbitrap Exploris 240 mass spectrometer.

2D-PAGE resolved two isoforms of mussel TPM and up to eight isoforms of clam TPM. The determined pI value of the dominant isoform of mussel TPM was 4.7 while the discrete band arising from the second TPM isoform was slightly shifted toward acidic pI and smaller molecular mass. The determined pI value of the three most dominant clam TPM isoforms was 4.8, the fourth isoform was slightly shifted toward a more basic pI value and lower protein molecular weight. The rest of the isoforms were slightly shifted toward more acidic pI and at a similar molecular weight as the three dominant isoforms.

The mass spectrometry results were obtained using PEAKS software using *de novo*, database, and SPIDER search. In the MS data evaluation, we tried to implement one of the promising approaches for resolving the protein amino acid sequences proposed by Tran and colleagues⁴ that relies on the principle of the Bruijn graph applied to *de novo* sequences. Unfortunately, this approach didn't lead to the identification of TPM isoform sequences since there was a low abundance of less dominant isoforms. Mass spectrometry results using database search (using a PDB library of all known TPM sequences) in dominant mussel TPM isoform identified 25 peptides which cover 42 % of amino acid (AA) sequence of TPM with NCBI accession P91958. Regarding less abundant mussel TPM isoform 21 peptides were identified which interestingly cover 36 % of the AA sequence of *Penaeus monodon*, NCBI accession AAX37288. Although up to 8 isoforms of clam TPM were been detected upon 2D-PAGE, 6 bands were successfully excised. In the most dominant clam TPM isoform 35 peptides were identified which cover 61 % of the AA sequence of TPM with NCBI accession BAH10157. Although the number of identified peptides in less present clam TPM isoforms decreased, peptides with different amino acids were discovered in isoforms three and five compared to peptides at the same position in the dominant isoform. Using sequence alignment of identified peptides in dominant and less abundant mussel and clam TPM isoforms it was possible to detect to some extent the substitution of particular AA among isoforms.

References

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3. González-Fernández, J.; et al. Are fish tropomyosins allergens? *Ann. Allergy Asthma Immunol.* 2016, 116 (1), 74-76.
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